

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE PROVISION OF PUBLIC SERVICES

Sagdullaev Ulugbek Axmadjon ogli

Republic of Uzbekistan, Samarkand Institute
of Economics and Service, Independent Researcher
Author's email address: ulugbeksagdullaev44@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15378180>

Abstract: In the world, public services are provided to individuals and legal entities in a modern market manner as a special type of service provision in the form of performing the functions of state and local authorities. The article provides a brief description of scientific and theoretical approaches to the provision of public services.

Key words: state, service, population, post-industrial, public services, service, service business, city, social initiative, citizen, initiative, transparency, accountability, society, “smart city”, social service, post-industrial.

Annotatsiya: Jahonda davlat xizmatlari xizmat ko'rsatishning maxsus turi sifatida jismoniy va yuridik shaxslarga davlat, shuningdek mahalliy hokimiyat organlarining funksiyalarini bajarish shaklidagi zamonaviy bozor uslubida taqdim etilmoqda. Maqolada davlat xizmatlarini ko'rsatish borasida ilmiy-nazariy yondashuvlar qisqacha bayoni keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat, xizmat, aholi, postindustrial, davlat xizmatlari, servis, servis biznes, shahar, ijtimoiy tashabbus, fuqaro, tashabbus, shaffoflik, hisobdorlik, jamiyat, “aqlli shahar”, ijtimoiy xizmat, postindustrial.

Аннотация: В мире государственные услуги предоставляются как особый вид услуг физическим и юридическим лицам в современном рыночном стиле в форме выполнения функций органов государственной власти и местного самоуправления. В статье дана краткая характеристика научно-теоретических подходов к предоставлению государственных услуг.

Ключевые слова: государство, сервис, население, постиндустриальный, государственные услуги, сервис, сервисный бизнес, город, социальная инициатива, гражданин, инициатива, прозрачность, подотчетность, общество, «умный город», социальный сервис, постиндустриальный.

Introduction. One of the main directions of reforms in the field of public administration in our country is to radically increase the efficiency of the civil service, develop a civil service model that meets the requirements of the present day, while analyzing national and foreign experience in organizing and

reforming the civil service. This is of strategic importance as it forms an updated and effective civil service system that meets the current level of development of our society and world standards of the rule of law.

It is clear to all of us that the system of political, socio-economic relations between the state and the population has been constantly updated throughout the development of mankind, improving into effective, productive and effective forms. In particular, the post-industrial nature of today's socio-economic development has created a "service feature" inherent in the market approach to relations between the population and the state.

Modern scientific literature, with a wide emphasis on the transition of the traditional administrative approach to a business approach, explains the post-industrial aspects of public administration by the use of concepts such as "business model of the state", "model of public service provision", "model of public service". Undoubtedly, there is no full-fledged scientific interpretation, explanation and definition of the "service nature" of relations between the state and the population, but it is noteworthy that in the practice of advanced foreign countries it has been implemented in practice as public service provision.

Main part. Conceptual approaches such as public services, business model of public administration, public service are largely aimed at further strengthening the values of national statehood, taking into account social support for citizens in administrative units, targeted use of budget funds on the basis of saving expenditures on management, and on the other hand, achieving utility based on increasing the subjective satisfaction of the population with the activities of state bodies.

The policy of transparency, openness and openness in public administration was previously defined as "...social initiative, citizen participation and initiative, transparency, accountability, participation" which primarily includes various mechanisms for implementing citizens' initiatives and the mutual rights and obligations of the parties. Therefore, it is appropriate to clarify their interrelationships and common aspects by comparing the essence of these terms (Table 1).

Table 1

Service-oriented business models of public administration¹

Types of public administration	Description
Serviced State	It reflects the provision of competent services to the

¹ Developed by the author

	population and entrepreneurs within the framework of the functions and tasks of the state. These services consist in determining the individual procedure for the use of material goods, goods and services, while simultaneously creating socio-economic benefits for members of society and for the state.
Business City	Cities can further enhance socio-economic life activities and create benefits by reducing negative environmental impacts through the introduction of various forms of intelligent services. In this case, cities fully cover all situations in the socio-economic life of the population with the provision of public services.
Smart City Model	According to this model, city government provides services to the population that are economically beneficial, socially unique, and environmentally sustainable. The main role in this is attributed to the city administration, which participates directly (e.g., developing various strategies/providing services/facilitating decision-making) and indirectly (providing regulatory and legal support) in creating socio-economic benefits.
“State-as-a-Service” Model	"In many countries, the state structure plays the role of the customer, the buyer, and the population or business entities play the role of the seller, the supplier."

In the studies of foreign scholars, the theory of modern public administration (administrative management) promotes a managerial approach and considers it “expedient to expand the participation of business entities in managing it, partially excluding the priority given to the creation and organization of material benefits for the population.”

At the current stage of social development, it is in many ways beneficial and expedient for the state to play the role of a service provider and supplier, and the population and business entities to play the role of consumers of these services. Because today, due to the increasing standard of living of the population and globalization, only some of the state’s permitting functions are of primary importance.

In this regard, the principle of “state - service provider” is widely applied as one of the most optimal solutions for public administration in a post-industrial society.

We can justify the priority given to the concept of providing public services by several aspects. Firstly, against the background of increasing multinational diversity in the world, in individual countries, centuries-old experiences of state administration do not have effective means to meet the growing new demands of society, so there is an attempt to switch to business models. Secondly, the achievement of international indicators assessing the effectiveness of state administration determines the foreign economic and political activity of the country, region. As a result, “... most countries of the world are constantly participating in methods of modernization of business processes of state administration (Business Process Reengineering), the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) rating, the World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators, the global e-government index, and the like” and improving the country's position in them requires a transition to a business model of management, decentralization of powers to the lowest possible level. Thirdly, service economy relations require “... both the improvement of traditional state functions and, where necessary, the expansion of the participation of the private sector.”

It should also be noted that the diversity of opinions in scientific sources regarding public administration, the business model of management and the managerial approach makes it difficult to choose the most appropriate one in the future and apply it in the conditions of a rapidly changing market environment. At the same time, the gradual transition of the state to a service model in many respects “... limits the possibility of transitioning to a large-scale provision of public services, which is somewhat contradictory to the principles of public management, and creating a unique “ecosystem” based on expanding the participation of citizens and business entities in management”.

In the legislation of Uzbekistan, the concept of “public service” was initially included in the “Regulations on the procedure for forming and maintaining a unified register of public services, forms and forms” attached to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 120 dated May 13, 2015. This regulation states that “public service is a service provided by state bodies to implement the functions of state bodies at the request of applicants by state administration, local government bodies and other state organizations.” At the same time, the definition also states that other organizations may also

provide public service if the functions of providing public services are assigned to them in accordance with the legislation. The regulation establishes that the result of providing public service is the implementation of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of applicants, expressed in the implementation of relevant actions by state bodies in accordance with the regulations on the provision of public services, including the provision of relevant information and documents to applicants.

D.D. Chvilyov put forward the issues of assessing the quality of public services, noting that “...the quality of public services should be assessed by factors such as the standard of living, number and density of the population in the region, the degree of saturation of the labor market, the technical and technological provision of services, and that the quality of public services reflects its usefulness.” In our opinion, D.D. Chvilyov’s approach to assessing the quality of public services leads to the assessment of the same type of public service at different quality levels in different regions or population locations and reduces the possibility of its expansion.

O.A. Kostin’s scientific research studied the issues of providing public services at the level of territorial self-government, and “...the provision of services related to the formation of quality living conditions for the local population” as well as the issues of planning and forecasting the population’s demand for municipal services and financing. In our opinion, the approaches put forward by O.A. Kostin are somewhat limited in their applicability in the mahalla system of our country, which largely envisages the provision of state services in regions that are financed by the state and receive appropriate budget subsidies.

A.A. Smirnova recognized that “...social service is an action or actions in the field of social services to provide permanent, periodic, one-time assistance, including emergency assistance, provided to a citizen to improve his living conditions and (or) expand his ability to independently provide for his basic life needs.” Social services include, for example, free travel on suburban railway transport, as well as to the place of treatment and intercity transport. In this definition, the main emphasis is placed on social services, with great importance attached to the needs of the population.

I.I. Savelev in his monograph “State and Municipal Services: Quality Analysis and Evaluation Analysis” defined “state service - a normatively established provision of a certain consumer with the use of a state approved

opportunity necessary to obtain a certain useful measurable result in relation to a certain state or municipal body”.

S.Y. Naumov noted that “...any action that a state body is obliged to perform in relation to a citizen or organization is everything that the recipient has the right to demand under the appropriate conditions. By law, the state includes: passport, benefits, registration as unemployed, registration of real estate, registration of mass media, as well as registration of marriage, subsidies, extracts, information, advice, consideration of appeals, explanations; other types of services”.

M.N. Ashirova studied the issues of the relationship between public services and material goods and the categories of public services, and presented the fact that public services are “...the implementation of the legal rights of consumers, carried out by a state body responsible for the quality of its provision at the request or initiative of consumers, and as a result, obtaining a certain privilege that has commodity properties” and acquire a characteristic of material goods. In our opinion, the emphasis in M.N. Ashirova’s approach on the provision of public services by state bodies leads to a limitation of the participation of non-governmental organizations in this area.

List of used literature:

1. Smirnova A.A. O sootnoshenii gosudarstvennykh uslug, funktsiy i polnomochiy organov ispolnitelnoy vlasti. Jurnal rossiyskogo prava №3 – 2015, 120-130 str.
2. Gosudarstvennyye i munisipalnyye uslugi: analiz i metodika osenki kachestva : monografiya / I.I.Savelyev. — Moskva : RUSAYNS, 2017. — 136 s.
3. Amelin R. V., Grigoryeva Ye. A., Podsumkova A. A., Filatova A. V., Channov S. Ye. Kommentariy k Federalnomu zakonu ot 27 iyulya 2010 g. № 210-FZ «Ob organizatsii predostavleniya gosudarstvennykh i munisipalnykh uslug» (postateynyy) / pod red. S. Yu. Naumova. Saratov, 2011. 214 r.
4. Ashirova, M.N. Institusionalizatsiya otnosheniy gosudarstva i potrebiteley yego uslug. Avtoreferat dissertatsii na soiskaniye uchenoy stepeni kandidata ekonomicheskix nauk. / Ashirova Mariya Nikolayevna. Yujno-Rossiyskiy institut upravleniya. Rostov-na-Donu – 2014.–26 s.
5. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2015 yil 13 maydagi 120-son qaroriga 1-ilova “Davlat xizmatlari, shakllari va blankalari yagona reyestrini shakllantirish va yuritish tartibi to‘g‘risida Nizom”
6. Sadler Dj. Povysheniye kachestva gosudarstvennykh uslug: opyt Velikobritanii. URL: http://vasilievaa.narod.ru/10_3_00.htm.

7. Ashirova M.N. Institucionalizatsiya otnosheniy gosudarstva i potrebiteley yego uslug. Avtoreferat dissertatsii na soiskaniye uchenoy stepeni kandidata ekonomicheskix nauk. / Ashirova Mariya Nikolayevna. Yujno-Rossiyskiy institut upravleniya. Rostov-na-Donu – 2014.–26 s.
8. BARAT-ALIYEVICH A. F., NODIROVNA M. S. THE ESSENCE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CONCEPTS OF INNOVATION, INNOVATION ACTIVITY AND INNOVATION ENTREPRENEURSHIP. – 2023.
9. SAIDAKHMEDOVICH S. T., NODIROVNA M. S. TOLIBOVNA TD THE REFORM OF PROFESSIONS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY, THE MOST IN DEMAND IN THE LABOR MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN //Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521). – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 6. – С. 278-289.
10. SAIDAKHMEDOVICH S. T., NODIROVNA M. S., TOLIBOVNA T. D. P. O. F. S. B. AS A FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN //Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521). – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 6. – С. 268-277.
11. Мирзаева Ш. Н., Ашуров С. З. Анализ Инвестиционного Климата В Узбекистане, Состояние И Перспективы //GlobalBiz Summit: Business and Economic Strategies for the Future. – 2025. – Т. 1. – С. 72-75.
12. ILKHAMOVNA S. Z., NODIROVNA M. S., KHURSHEDOVICH A. A. TOURISM CLUSTERS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY //International Conference on Adaptive Learning Technologies. – 2024. – Т. 5. – С. 133-141.
13. ILKHAMOVNA S. Z., NODIROVNA M. S., KUVONCH R. EXPANSION OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN THE CONTEXT OF INNOVATIVE CHANGES IN UZBEKISTAN //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2024. – Т. 48. – С. 90-98.
14. ILKHAMOVNA S. Z., NODIROVNA M. S., ALIASKAR M. IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF THE THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF MEASURING SOCIAL CAPITAL //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2024. – Т. 49. – С. 167-174.
15. ILKHAMOVNA S. Z., NODIROVNA M. S., MUROD S. DIGITALIZATION OF SOCIAL TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE SERVICE SECTOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2024. – Т. 48. – С. 80-89.
16. ILKHAMOVNA S. Z., NODIROVNA M. S., FIRUZA A. ECOTOURISM AS A TOOL FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND POVERTY REDUCTION //International Conference on Adaptive Learning Technologies. – 2024. – Т. 5. – С. 123-132.

17. ILKHAMOVNA S. Z., NODIROVNA M. S. SUBHONZODA SH THE EXPERIENCE OF OTHER COUNTRIES IN THE LEGAL REGULATION OF ECOTOURISM //BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 5. – C. 122-131.

18. Nodirovna M. S. Foreign Experience in Supporting Entrepreneurship and Business Activity of Women. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal Volume2, Issue 5 Year2023 ISSN: 2835-3013 <https://univerpubl.com/index.php/synergy> <https://scholar.google.com/citations>.

